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FABRICATION AND HYDROPHILIC CHARACTERIZATION OF NANOPARTICLE-FILLD POYOMER COMPOSITES

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Introduction

□ Back ground

- Polymers are generally hydrophobic
- It is difficult to replace glass lens of endoscopic.
- In order to solve these subjects, there is a method of making oxide nanoparticles polymer composite to provide polymer hydrophilization.
- But the detailed characteristics of the oxide particles and the polymer composites are not known.

https://sc02.alicdn.com/kf/HTB181cGQXXXXc5aFXX760XFXxa/Video-Laryngoscope-with-cheap-price.png_350x350.png

□ Objective

The following two will be clarified to make the hydrophilic oxide nanoparticle filled polymer composite material.

1. Hydrophilic effect of oxide nanoparticles
2. hydrophilicity and optical properties of the polymer composites

Experimental

□ Sample preparation

1. Surface modification

The substrate was dipped in TEOS 1wt% ethanol solution to semi-carbonate.

2. Layer-by-Layer Self-Assembly

The nanoparticles stuck to the base material by the method below.

□ Material

Base material : Polycarbonate sheet

Surface modification : Tetraethyl orthosilicate (TEOS)

Cationic solution : Poly-(diallyldimethyl-ammonium chloride) solution (Mw=100,000)

□ Nano particle

Materials	Avarage size [nm]	Shape
SiO ₂	12	Spherical
SiO ₂	50	Spherical
SiO ₂	80	Spherical
SiO ₂	100	Spherical
TiO ₂	80	Non-spherical
ZrO ₂	90	Non-spherical
SnO ₂	120	Non-spherical
ZnO	75	Non-spherical

Experimental

□ Preparation of composite materials

The sample was prepared using a cast method.

□ Material

Polymer: Poly methyl methacrylate particle (8nm)

Solvent: 2-Butanone (MEK)

Oxide nanoparticles:

MEK dispersion SiO₂ (70~100nm)

Hydrophobic modification SiO₂ (15nm, Aggregated particles 500nm)

Results and Discussion

□ Hydrophilic effect of oxide nanoparticles

SiO₂ [100nm]

TiO₂ [80nm]

Fig.1. Particle distribution on surface of samples

Fig.2. Influences of surface area and material type on contact angle

- ✓ TiO₂ had a high hydrophilic effect.
- ✓ In addition, in the case of SiO₂, by reducing the particles size and increasing the specific surface area, it was possible to obtain the same hydrophilic effect.

Results and Discussion

□ hydrophilicity and optical of the polymer composites

Fig.3. Effect of compounding rate on contact angle before polishing

Fig.4. Effect of compounding rate on contact angle after polishing

Polishing

- ✓ Fig. 3 shows water contact angle of the hot pressed samples of PMMA with and without the composite processes for the nanoparticles. However, the water contact angle reduced after polishing. This reason would be explained that the particles almost didn't exist on the surfaces.

Results and Discussion

□ hydrophilicity and optical of the polymer composites

Fig.5. Influence of compounding rate on contact angle and transmittance

- ✓ As the composition of nanoparticles increased, the contact angle and the transmittance decreased.

Conclusion

- ❑ It has been confirmed that the type and the particle size of the oxide nanoparticles influence the hydrophilicity.
- ❑ In the nanoparticle composite material, it was revealed that there is a problem in coexistence of hydrophilicity and optical properties (transmittance).